

Detailed Event Monitors Analysis (Supplemental Material to the RTSS 2025 publication titled: “EMR: Removing Multicollinear Event Monitors to Improve Timing Modelling of Real-Time Systems”)

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Abstract—This document provides supplemental material to the following work published at RTSS [1]. In particular, it details the set of Event Monitors (EMs) that have been filtered out by the proposed technique, EMR, and those EMs for which EMR found a linear relation.

I. INTRODUCTION: LIST OF EMS IN THE NXP T2080

Our work [1] targets the NXP T2080 Reference Board [2]–[5]. The T2080 equips 262 EMs per core that track cycles (running, stall, idle, ...), instructions (fetched, executed, committed, ...), and other events (e.g., number of overflows, cache allocations, hits, and misses). The complete list of EMs is provided in the e6500 manual [3], Section 9.12.6 Table 9-61 “Performance monitor event selection (by category)”. For the sake of completeness of this document, we list them in Tables VIII–XV, including for each event its event ID, name, and a short description.

In terms of the experimental setup we use, it is presented in Section IV of the main document of this work [1]. The output of EMR when applied to these kernels is presented in the following sections.

II. FILTERED OUT EMS

We first apply the two preliminary filters aimed at removing features that provide no information individually as shown in Section III.A in [1].

We eliminate 132 non-active EMs (we detected no constant non-nil EM), which are show in Table I. Nil EMs relate to unused components and non-triggered activities of our applications, which are the following.

- Memory system events like TLB+MMU (translation), fetch, stashes, and the like, which correspond to EM_{11-66} , EM_{97-99} , $EM_{239-269}$, $EM_{461-511}$ in Table I. For instance, our programs do not use stashes ($EM_{97,99,474,475,510} = 0$) and are single-threaded, hence with negligible impact on coherence ($EM_{478-494} = 0$). Note that intervals of EMs refer only to those listed in Table I.

- Vector operations (not used by our programs) events, which correspond to $EM_{112-119}$ and $EM_{198-205}$ in Table I.
- Interrupts (not generated by our programs), which correspond to EM_{86-90} in Table I
- Some branch predictor features which correspond to EM_{68-72} in Table I.
- Management of some specific external events, which correspond to EM_{6-7} in Table I.
- Events related to the interaction across multiple threads (we use single-threaded programs), which correspond to $EM_{100-105}$, $EM_{225-226}$ and EM_{274} in Table I.
- Performance Monitoring Counter (PMC) overflows, which correspond to EM_{82-85} and EM_{91-92} in Table I.
- Access very specific registers like instruction and data compare registers, or the debug event selection register, which correspond to $EM_{136-155}$ in Table I.
- Use of very infrequent instructions, such as management of denormalized floating point data, decorated loads and stores, and the like, which correspond to $EM_{163-168}$ and $EM_{176-188}$ in Table I.
- Some miscellaneous EMs related to power modes or the generation of specific events beyond the L2 cache, which correspond to EM_{172} and EM_{272} in Table I.

III. RELATION AMONG EMS

Beyond identifying redundant EMs, EMR also unveils a variety of relations among them. These relations range from straightforward equivalences between counters that measure the same phenomenon, to more complex linear dependencies that reveal hidden connections between different event types. Studying these relations is essential for both reducing the dimensionality of the EM set and for gaining insights into the microarchitectural behavior of the T2080. We first discuss simple equivalence relations that allow the construction of a directed graph of dependencies and the selection of representative EMs. We then move to more general linear relations, including type decompositions into subtypes, and highlight both intuitive and counter-intuitive cases discovered by EMR.

TABLE I: Negligible and Constant Features

ID	Event Name	ID	Event Name
6	PM_EVENT transitions	150	DVT2 detected
7	PM_EVENT cycles	151	DVT3 detected
11	Number of CQ redirects	152	DVT4 detected
29	Touches translated	153	DVT5 detected
30	Cache ops translated	154	DVT6 detected
31	Cache-inhibited accesses translated	155	DVT7 detected
32	Guarded loads translated	156	Cycles completion stalled (Nexus)
33	Write-through stores translated	163	FPU denorm input
34	Misaligned load or store accesses translated	164	FPU denorm output
36	Fetch hits on prefetches	165	FPU FPSCR full stall
37	Fetch prefetches generated	168	FPU instruction generates flags
45	Load guarded miss when the load is not yet at the bottom of the CB	172	PW20 count
48	DTLB miss times	176	Decorated loads
49	DTLB busy times	177	Decorated stores
50	Second part of misaligned access when first part missed in cache	179	stbcx., sthcx., stwcx., or stdcx. successful
53	Load guarded miss when the load is not yet at the bottom of the CB	180	stbcx., sthcx., stwcx., or stdcx. unsuccessful
56	DTLB miss cycles	184	Cache ops completed
57	DTLB busy cycles	188	SFX double-cycle micro-ops completed
58	Second part of misaligned access when first part missed in cache	198	Altivec instructions completed
60	Instruction L1 cache reloads from fetch	199	Altivec VSFX instructions completed
62	IMMU TLB-4K reloads	200	Altivec VCFX instructions completed
63	IMMU VSP reloads	201	Altivec VPU instructions completed
64	DMMU TLB-4K reloads	202	Altivec VFPU instructions completed
65	DMMU VSP reloads	203	VR loads completed
66	L2MMU error misses	204	VR stores completed
68	blr taken	205	VSCR[SAT] set
70	Target blr mispredict (link stack)	225	Load thread miss collision
72	BTB hit with phantom branch	226	inter-thread status array collision
82	PMC0 overflow	239	LRSAQ full cycles
83	PMC1 overflow	240	LRSAQ full times
84	PMC2 overflow	246	STQ collision not-forwardable (times not forwardable)
85	PMC3 overflow	250	STQ collision non-forwardable (cycles not forwardable)
86	Interrupts taken	253	Inter-thread doubleword bank collisions
87	External input interrupts taken	254	Instruction L1 cache misses
88	Critical input interrupts taken	256	IMMU misses
89	System call and trap interrupts	257	IMMU TLB-4K hits
90	Transitions of TBL bit selected by PMGC0[TBSEL]	259	IMMU cycles spent in hardware tablewalk
91	PMC4 overflow	260	DMMU misses
92	PMC5 overflow	261	DMMU TLB-4K hits
97	Stash hit to L1 Data Cache	263	DMMU cycles spent in hardware tablewalk
99	Stash requests to L1 Data Cache	264	L2MMU misses
100	Number of times LSU thread priority switched	265	L2MMU hits in L2MMU-4K
101	Number of cycles both threads had FPU requests and one was denied	266	L2MMU hits in L2MMU-VSP
102	Number of cycles both threads had VPERM requests and one was denied	267	L2MMU indirect misses
103	Number of cycles both threads had VGEN requests and one was denied	268	L2MMU indirect valid misses
104	Number of cycles both threads had CFX requests and one was denied	269	LRAT misses
105	Number of cycles both threads had Fetch requests and one was denied	272	Cycles LMQ loses DLINK arbitration due to SGB
112	Cycles Altivec issue stalled	274	Cycles thread loses DLINK arbitration due to other thread
114	Cycles VPERM schedule stalled	444	ILINK request
115	Cycles VGEN schedule stalled	461	L2 instruction accesses
116	Cycles VPU instruction waits for operands	463	L2 instruction misses
117	Cycles VFPU instruction waits for operands	469	L2 instruction accesses per thread
118	Cycles VSFX instruction waits for operands	471	L2 instruction misses per thread
119	Cycles VCFX instruction waits for operands	474	L2 stash requests
136	IAC5s detected	475	L2 stash requests downgraded to snoops
137	IAC6s detected	478	L2 snoops causing SINT
138	IAC7s detected	480	Stall for BIB cycles
139	IAC8s detected	482	Stall for RLT cycles
140	IAC1s detected	484	Stall for RLFQ cycles
141	IAC2s detected	486	Stall for DTQ cycles
142	IAC3s detected	488	Stall for COB cycles
143	IAC4s detected	490	Stall for WDB cycles
144	DAC1s detected	494	Stall for SNPQ cycles
145	DAC2s detected	509	BIU master instruction-side requests
148	DVT0 detected	510	Stash requests
149	DVT1 detected	511	Snoop requests

A. Single-feature relations

These relations allow forming a directed graph and choosing the appropriate representatives of each connected component. These relations led to the elimination of another 30 EMs, leaving 100 EMs remaining. The complete set of relations

is reported in Tables II and III. Examples of single-feature relations include the following:

- (1) FP operations ($EM_{161} = EM_{192}$): Finished FPU operations, i.e. *FPU finish* (EM_{161}), and completed operations, i.e. *FPU instructions completed* (EM_{192}), match

since our applications do not execute FPU instructions under mispredicted branches.

- (2) Cycles ($EM_{216} = EM_{217}$): Idle cycles for unused components reflect identical values, matching the execution cycles. For instance, *cycles VPU idle* (EM_{216}) and *cycles VFPU idle* (EM_{217}) match.
- (3) Some cache events ($EM_{445} = 2 \times EM_{41}$). The number of reload (RLINK) requests from L2 to DL1, *RLINK request* (EM_{445}), is twice the number of DL1 reloads, *Data L1 cache reloads* (EM_{41}).

Some other relations produced by EMR are counter-intuitive, such as for instance, $EM_{13} = EM_{122}$, which indicates that the number of taken branches finished (EM_{13}) matches the cycles when the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).

B. General linear relations

We find 40 general linear relations, 36 of which are independent. We analyze those relations in Tables IV–VII, where for each relation we indicate whether it is explicable, whether it is intuitive or counter-intuitive, and we provide a short description.

Some example relations identified relate to *type decomposition into subtypes* which is a challenging task when understanding EMs. In particular, determining whether an EM that measures a given event type can be decomposed into the addition of EMs that track event subtypes, e.g., cache accesses can be split among reads and writes, or hits and misses.

1) *Load and Stores*: For the count of loads and stores we found these relations.

- Load-Store operations ($EM_{181} = EM_{195} + EM_{182} + EM_{183} + EM_{185}$). The total number of *LSU micro-ops completed* (EM_{181}) matches the addition of *FPR loads and stores completed* (EM_{195}), the number of *GPR loads completed* (EM_{182}), the number of *GPR stores completed* (EM_{183}) and the number of *Memory barriers completed* (EM_{185}).
- FPR loads-store operations ($EM_{195} = EM_{196} + EM_{197}$): The total number *FPR loads and stores completed* (EM_{195}) matches the addition of the number of *FPR single-precision loads and stores completed* (EM_{196}) and the number of *FPR double-precision loads and stores completed* (EM_{197}).

Note that, while the latter is an intuitive relation, the former is far less obvious, and it may not be easy to reason about it a priori without the support of EMR.

2) *Store Gather Buffer*: The Store Gather Buffer (SGB) temporarily keeps stores operations in the core before they are sent to the cache system. The EM tracking promotions, (EM_{230}) *SGB promotions*, seems to capture all promotions, which is then broken down into different sub-types: *SGB in-order promotions* (EM_{231}), *SGB out-of-order promotions* (EM_{232}), *SGB high-priority promotions* (EM_{233}), *SGB miso promotions* (EM_{234}), *SGB watermark promotions* (EM_{235}), and *SGB overflow promotions* (EM_{236}).

Whether those are disjoint sub-types, or sub-types resulting from different classification criteria for the promotions is undocumented. However, we would expect EM_{230} to match the addition of some of those EMs. For instance, one would expect $EM_{230} = EM_{231} + EM_{232}$ to hold, since total promotions should match the addition of in-order and out-of-order ones. However, and surprisingly, this relation is not obtained by EMR since it does not hold. This is an example, of an a-priori intuitive relation based on EM description, that EMR disproved. On the other hand, EMR finds the relation $EM_{232} = EM_{185} + EM_{233} + EM_{235} + EM_{236}$, which relates out of order promotions with high-priority promotions, watermark promotions, overflow promotions and the number of *memory barriers completed* (EM_{185}), which is quite counter-intuitive.

Other unexpected casuistic emerge with EMR, such as $EM_{243} = EM_{245} + EM_{248}$, which relates the number of times an event occurs (forwardable collisions) in the store queue (EM_{243}) with the addition of this very same event with data ready (EM_{245}), and the number of cycles when this event occurs and data is not ready (EM_{248}). It is unexpected that the latter corresponds to cycles instead of times. Hence, with this counter-intuitive relation, EMR indirectly suggests that forwardable store queue collisions when data is not ready last for one cycle each.

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TABLE II: Description of the single-feature relations (Part 1).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_2 = EM_{278}$	Y	Y	N	The number of instructions completed (EM_2) matches instructions decoded (EM_{278}).
$EM_3 = EM_{278}$	Y	Y	N	The number of micro-ops completed (EM_3), typically one per instruction, matches instructions decoded (EM_{278}).
$EM_8 = EM_{12}$	Y	Y	N	The number of branch instructions completed (EM_8) matches the number of branch instructions finished (EM_{12}), where the latter also counts speculative branches finished.
$EM_{13} = EM_{122}$	N	N	Y	The number of taken branches finished (EM_{13}) matches the cycles when the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).
$EM_{14} = EM_{17}$	N	N	Y	The number of unconditional branches that miss in the BTB (EM_{14}) match the number of branches of any kind that hit the BTB (EM_{17}).
$EM_{16} = EM_{122}$	N	N	Y	The number of branches with direction mispredicted in the BTB (EM_{16}) match the number of cycles the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).
$EM_{67} = EM_{122}$	N	N	Y	The number of branches taken (EM_{67}) matches the number of cycles the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).
$EM_{69} = EM_{122}$	N	N	Y	The number of branches with target mispredicted in the BTB (EM_{69}) match the number of cycles the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).
$EM_{71} = EM_{122}$	N	N	Y	The number of branches taken and mispredicted in the BTB (EM_{71}) match the number of cycles the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}).
$EM_{111} = EM_{166}$	Y	Y	N	Number of cycles the FPU issue is stalled because instructions are not ready (EM_{111}) matches the number of cycles the FPU issue is stalled because either instructions are not ready or the FPU is busy (EM_{166}).
$EM_{161} = EM_{192}$	Y	Y	N	The number of finished FPU operations (EM_{161}) matches completed operations (EM_{192}) since benchmarks do not execute FPU instructions under mispredicted branches.
$EM_{186} = EM_{187}$	Y	Y	N	The number of simple integer instructions (EM_{186}) matches single-cycle simple integer instructions (EM_{187}).
$EM_{216} = EM_{217}$	Y	Y	N	The number of cycles the VPU idle (EM_{216}) and cycles VFPU idle (EM_{217}) match since both components are unused.
$EM_{217} = EM_{219}$	Y	Y	N	The number of cycles the VFPU the idle (EM_{217}) and cycles complex-instruction integer vector unit is idle (EM_{219}) match since both components are unused.
$EM_{218} = EM_{219}$	Y	Y	N	The number of cycles simple-instruction integer vector unit is idle (EM_{218}) and cycles complex-instruction integer vector unit is idle (EM_{219}) match since both components are unused.

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TABLE III: Description of the single-feature relations (Part 2).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_{222} = EM_{224}$	Y	Y	N	L1 data load misses (EM_{222}) match the number of times a load allocates an entry in the load memory queue (EM_{224}) to fetch data.
$EM_{227} = EM_{230}$	Y	Y	N	SGB allocations (EM_{227}) and SGB promotions (EM_{230}) match since all stores using the SGB cause both allocation and promotion.
$EM_{234} = 2 \cdot EM_{185}$	N	N	Y	SGB miso promotions (EM_{234}) match twice the number of memory barriers (EM_{185}). Both events occur seldom and this relation is not intuitive.
$EM_{244} = EM_{248}$	Y	N	N	Number of times a store queue collision occurs and the data is ready (EM_{244}) matches the number of cycles such cases occur (EM_{248}); meaning such cases last one cycle in our benchmarks. Highly benchmark-dependent.
$EM_{445} = 2 \cdot EM_{41}$	Y	Y	N	RLINK requests (EM_{445}) are twice the number of DL1 reloads (EM_{41}).
$EM_{456} = EM_{465}$	Y	Y	N	L2 hits (EM_{456}) and L2 hits per thread (EM_{465}) match since only one thread is used.
$EM_{457} = EM_{466}$	Y	Y	N	L2 misses (EM_{457}) and L2 misses per thread (EM_{466}) match since only one thread is used.
$EM_{458} = EM_{467}$	Y	Y	N	L2 demand accesses (EM_{458}) and L2 demand accesses per thread (EM_{467}) match since only one thread is used.
$EM_{462} = EM_{470}$	Y	Y	N	L2 data accesses (EM_{462}) and L2 data accesses per thread (EM_{470}) match since only one thread is used.
$EM_{464} = EM_{473}$	Y	Y	N	L2 data misses (EM_{464}) and requests to the CCF (EM_{473}) match since each L2 data miss causes one CCF request to fetch the data.
$EM_{472} = EM_{473}$	Y	Y	N	L2 data misses per thread (EM_{472}) and requests to the CCF (EM_{473}) match since each L2 data miss causes one CCF request, with a single thread.
$EM_{476} = EM_{479}$	Y	Y	N	L2 snoop hits (EM_{476}) and L2 snoop pushes (EM_{479}) match since benchmarks do not create coherence-related invalidations.
$EM_{477} = EM_{479}$	Y	Y	N	L2 snoops causing MINT (EM_{477}) and L2 snoop pushes (EM_{479}) match since benchmarks do not create coherence-related invalidations.
$EM_{506} = EM_{508}$	Y	Y	N	Accesses to the CCF interface (EM_{506}) match data accesses to the CCF interface (EM_{508}) since instructions hit in L1 and create no CCF accesses.
$EM_{460} = EM_{468}$	Y	Y	N	Store allocates (EM_{460}) match store allocates per thread (EM_{468}) since only one thread is used.

TABLE IV: General linear relations between EM counters and their explanations (Part 1).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_{191} = EM_{187} + EM_{190}$	Y	Y	N	The number of simple plus complex instructions (EM_{191}) matches the addition of single-cycle simple instructions (EM_{187}) and all complex instructions (EM_{190}). Note that EM_{191} should also include double-cycle simple instructions, but, according to the documentation, all multi-cycle instructions are regarded as complex, so no simple double-cycle instruction exists to our knowledge.
$EM_{278} = EM_{112} + EM_{181} + EM_{191} + EM_{192}$	Y	Y	N	The number of decoded instructions (EM_{278}) matches the addition of the number of branch instructions (EM_{112}), the number of loads and stores (EM_{181}), the number of integer arithmetic instructions (EM_{191}), and the number of arithmetic FPR instructions (EM_{192}).
$EM_9 = 1EM_{182} + 1EM_{193}$	Y	Y	N	The total number of load instructions (EM_9) matches the addition of integer load instructions (EM_{182}) and floating-point load instructions (EM_{193}).
$EM_{10} = EM_{183} + EM_{194}$	Y	Y	N	The total number of store instructions (EM_{10}) matches the addition of integer store instructions (EM_{183}) and floating-point store instructions (EM_{194}).
$EM_{193} = EM_{192} + EM_{194}$	Y	N	N	FPR loads completed (EM_{193}) matches the number of FPR instructions (EM_{192}) and FPR stores (EM_{194}). Rather than a general relation, this one reflects a specific relation holding for our benchmarks by chance since the number of FPR stores used is negligible, and we don't use arithmetic FPR instructions, so ultimately virtually all FPR instructions are FPR loads.
$EM_{181} = EM_{195} + EM_{182} + EM_{183} + EM_{185}$	Y	Y	N	The number of loads and stores microops completed (EM_{181}) matches the addition of FPR loads and stores completed (EM_{195}), GPR loads completed (EM_{182}), GPR stores completed (EM_{183}), and the number of memory barriers completed (EM_{185}), where the latter is always a very low value (typically 1).
$EM_{195} = EM_{196} + EM_{197}$	Y	Y	N	The total number FPR loads and stores completed (EM_{195}) matches the addition of the number of FPR single-precision loads and stores completed (EM_{196}) and the number of FPR double-precision loads and stores completed (EM_{197}).
$EM_{26} = EM_{27} + EM_{28}$	Y	Y	N	The total number of translated memory operations (EM_{26}) matches the addition of loads (EM_{27}) and stores (EM_{28}) translated.

TABLE V: General linear relations between EM counters and their explanations (Part 2).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_{221} = EM_{223} + EM_{224}$	Y	Y	N	DL1 cache misses (EM_{221}) matches the number of DL1 store cache misses (EM_{223}) and loads that allocate an entry in the Load Memory Queue (LMQ), EM_{224} . Note that, generally, we would expect all load misses, but a first load miss to a line allocates an entry in the LMQ and is counted as miss, and other “theoretical load misses” to the same cache line hit the LMQ entry in practice and are not regarded as misses since once the first load miss is served, all the rest to the same line become hits.
$EM_{12} = EM_{17} + EM_{122}$	Y	N	N	The number of branch instructions (EM_{12}) matches the addition of hits in the branch history buffer (BTB), so EM_{17} , and the number of cycles where the instruction buffer is empty (EM_{122}). EM_{17} has a one-to-one relation with branches experiencing BTB hits. On the other hand, upon a BTB miss, speculated instructions in the IB must be flushed, so it gets empty. Whether the IB is empty for exactly one cycle in those cases is more a consequence of the particular benchmarks used rather than a general rule.
$EM_{466} = 4EM_{185} + EM_{473}$	Y	Y	N	The number of L2 cache misses (EM_{466}) matches the addition of the number of accesses to the CCF beyond the L2 cache (EM_{473}) and 4 times the number of memory barriers. Note that memory barriers are only used once per benchmark at the end to secure that all memory instructions complete, and hence, any small variation in any EM may lead to weird artifacts with this EM , such as a relatively large multiplier (e.g., 4 in this case). In practice, we expect an almost one-to-one relation between EM_{466} and EM_{473} .
$EM_{507} = EM_{185} + EM_{473}$	Y	Y	N	The number of accesses to the L2 CCF interface (EM_{507}) matches the addition of the CCF accesses (EM_{473}) and memory barriers (EM_{185}). As said before, there is only one memory barrier per benchmark and this may create weird artifacts with this EM since, in practice, we expect a virtually one-to-one relation between EM_{507} and EM_{473} .
$EM_{443} = EM_{185} + EM_{470}$	Y	Y	N	The number of CCF accesses for data requests (EM_{443}) matches the number of L2 data accesses (EM_{470}) and the number of memory barriers (EM_{185}). The latter (EM_{185}) can be ignored as said before. The match between EM_{443} and EM_{470} is expected since L2 load accesses (EM_{470}) trigger a memory coherence request using the DLINK monitored by EM_{443} .

TABLE VI: General linear relations between EM counters and their explanations (Part 3).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_{467} = 4EM_{185} + EM_{470}$	Y	N	N	The number of L2 accesses (EM_{467}) matches the addition of the L2 data accesses (EM_{470}) and four times the memory barriers (EM_{185}). EM_{185} has a negligible value and can be ignored. Since benchmarks fit in L1 cache, there are virtually no instruction accesses to L2, so L2 total accesses match L2 data accesses.
$EM_{232} = EM_{185} + EM_{233} + EM_{235} + EM_{236}$	N	Y	N	This relates out-of-order promotions (EM_{232}) with high-priority (EM_{233}), watermark (EM_{235}), and overflow promotions (EM_{236}), plus the number of memory barriers (EM_{185}), which is counter-intuitive.
$EM_{230} = EM_{231} + EM_{233} + EM_{235} + EM_{236}$	Y	N	Y	SGB total promotions (EM_{230}) match the addition of a subset of SGB promotion categories (EM_{231} , EM_{233} , EM_{235} , EM_{236}). While this is generally expected, why this particular subset is chosen is unclear.
$EM_{122} = EM_{15} + EM_{17}$	N	N	Y	The number of cycles with the instruction buffer empty (EM_{122}) matches the addition of branch misses (EM_{15}) and BTB hits (EM_{17}), which is counter-intuitive.
$EM_{470} = EM_{465} + EM_{473}$	Y	Y	N	The number of L2 data accesses (EM_{470}) matches the addition of L2 hits (EM_{465}) and accesses from L2 to the request to fetch the data CCF (EM_{473}), roughly corresponding to L2 misses.
$EM_{247} = EM_{248} + EM_{249}$	Y	Y	N	A specific cycle counter for the store queue (EM_{247}) matches the addition of two other cycle counters for the same event: when data is ready (EM_{248}) and when data is not ready (EM_{249}).
$EM_{508} = EM_{479} + EM_{507}$	Y	N	N	Data requests to the CCF interface (EM_{508}) match the addition of all types of CCF requests (EM_{507}) and snoop pushes for coherence (EM_{479}). This holds due to the benchmarks used, making EM_{507} and EM_{508} close.
$EM_{459} = 3EM_{185} + EM_{467} + EM_{508}$	Y	Y	N	L2 data accesses (EM_{459}) match the addition of accesses from the core side (EM_{467}) and from the CCF interface side (EM_{508}). Memory barriers (EM_{185}) occur rarely and can be neglected.
$EM_{243} = EM_{245} + EM_{248}$	N	N	Y	The number of times an event occurs in the store queue (EM_{243}) matches the number of times it occurs with data ready (EM_{245}), and the number of cycles when data is not ready (EM_{248}). It is unexpected that the latter corresponds to cycles instead of event counts.

TABLE VII: General linear relations between EM counters and their explanations (Part 4).

Relation	Explicable	Intuitive	Counter-intuitive	Description
$EM_{219} = EM_{12} + EM_{214}$	N	N	Y	The number of cycles the vector unit is idle (EM_{219}) matches the addition of branches finished (EM_{12}), of cycles another component is idle (EM_{214}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{262} = EM_{17} + EM_{27} + EM_{223} + 2EM_{245}$	N	N	Y	Hits in one of the memory management unit tables (EM_{262}) matches the addition of several uncorrelated EMs for branches, loads, stores, and store queue events, a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{229} = EM_{46} + EM_{236}$	N	N	Y	SGB overflows (EM_{229}) match the addition of SGB overflow promotions (EM_{236}), store translations when the store queue is full (EM_{46}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{28} = EM_{223} + EM_{243}$	N	N	Y	Stores translated (EM_{28}) matches the addition of L1 store misses (EM_{223}), a type of events in the store queue (EM_{243}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{236} = EM_{229}$	Y	N	Y	SGB overflow promotions (EM_{236}) match the addition of SGB overflows (EM_{229}) and a large constant. These EMs are related, but the constant depends on specific benchmarks.
$EM_{241} = EM_{237}$	N	N	Y	The number of cycles the forward age queue is full (EM_{241}) matches to some extent the Dlink age queue (EM_{237}).
$EM_{52} = EM_{241}$	N	N	Y	Load misses with the load queue full (EM_{52}) matches to some extent the number of cycles the forward age queue is full (EM_{241}).
$EM_{479} = EM_{468}$	N	N	Y	The number of L2 snoop pushes (EM_{479}) matches to some extent the L2 store allocations (EM_{468}).
$EM_1 = EM_{219}$	Y	N	N	The number of processor cycles (EM_1) matches the addition of the number of cycles the vector unit is idle (EM_{219}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{126} = EM_{219}$	N	N	Y	The number of processor cycles a subtype of instructions spend in the instruction buffer (EM_{126}) matches the addition of the number of cycles the vector unit is idle (EM_{219}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{55} = 3EM_{245} + EM_{249} + 2EM_{251} + EM_{479}$	N	N	Y	The number of cycles there is an address collision between loads and stores (EM_{55}) matches the addition of several subtypes of store queue collisions (EM_{245} and EM_{249}), a subtype of address collisions (EM_{251}), L2 snoop pushes (EM_{479}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{223} = EM_{235} + EM_{236} + EM_{468}$	N	N	Y	L1 store misses (EM_{223}) matches the addition of some SGB promotion types (EM_{235} and EM_{236}), L2 store allocates (EM_{468}), a relation that holds with non-negligible variability.
$EM_{242} = EM_{238}$	Y	N	N	The number of times the forward age queue is full (EM_{242}) is very similar to the number of times the Dlink age queue is full (EM_{238}).
$EM_{224} = EM_{41}$	Y	N	N	The number of loads allocating an entry into the load memory queue (EM_{224}) is loosely similar to the number of L1 reloads (EM_{41}).

TABLE VIII: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 1–30) [2]

ID	Event	Description
1	Processor cycles	Every processor cycle
2	Instructions completed	Completed instructions (counts 0, 1, or 2 per cycle)
3	Micro-ops completed	Completed micro-ops
5	Micro-ops decoded	Micro-ops decoded
6	PM_EVENT transitions	0→1 transitions on the pm_event input
7	PM_EVENT cycles	Processor cycles when pm_event is asserted
8	Branch instructions completed	Completed branch instructions
9	Load micro-ops completed	Completed load micro-ops
10	Store micro-ops completed	Completed store micro-ops
11	CQ redirects	Fetch redirects from completion unit (e.g., sc, rfi, interrupts)
12	Branches finished	All branch instructions
13	Taken branches finished	All taken branch instructions
14	Uncond. branches BTB miss	Taken branches not allocated in BTB
15	Branch mispredictions	Mispredicted branches (direction, target, IAB). Not branches mispredicted as type.
16	Branch dir. mispredicted	Branch mispredicted due to direction prediction
17	BTB hits / pseudo-hits	Branches that hit in BTB or miss but are not taken (pseudo-hit)
18	Decode stall cycles	Cycles IQ not empty but 0 instructions decoded
19	SFX/CFX issue stall cycles	Cycles SFX/CFX IQ not empty but 0 issued
20	Branch issue stall cycles	Cycles Branch IQ not empty but 0 issued
21	SFX0 sched. stall cycles	Cycles SFX0 not empty but 0 scheduled
22	SFX1 sched. stall cycles	Cycles SFX1 not empty but 0 scheduled
23	CFX sched. stall cycles	Cycles CFX not empty but 0 scheduled
24	LSU sched. stall cycles	Cycles LSU not empty but 0 scheduled
25	BU sched. stall cycles	Cycles BU not empty but 0 scheduled
26	Total translated	LSU micro-ops reaching LSU1 second stage (counted once even if replayed/misaligned)
27	Loads translated	Cacheable load micro-ops translated (excl. WT)
28	Stores translated	Cacheable store micro-ops translated (excl. WT)
29	Touches translated	Cacheable touch instr. translated (e.g., dcbt, dcbst, icbt). Excl. no-ops or ls variants.
30	Cache ops translated	Cache ops translated (e.g., dcba, dcbb, dcbl, dcbs, dcbsz variants)

TABLE IX: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 31–100) [2]

ID	Event	Description
31	Cache-inhibited accesses	CI load/store accesses translated
32	Guarded loads	Guarded + decorated CI loads translated
33	Write-through stores	Write-through stores translated
34	Misaligned accesses	Misaligned load/store translated
35	Fetch 2x4 hits	Second half of fetch used
36	Fetch hits on prefetches	Prefetch already in ILFB
37	Fetch prefetches	Prefetches generated
41	Data L1 reloads	Data cache reloads
44	Load miss (queue full)	Stalls on load queue full
45	Guarded load miss	Stalls on guarded loads
46	Store queue full	Stalls on store queue full
47	Address collision	Load/store collision stalls
48	DTLB miss (stalls)	Stalls due to DTLB miss
49	DTLB busy (stalls)	Stalls due to DTLB busy
50	Misaligned 2nd part	Second part miss in cache
52	Load miss (cycles)	Cycles stalled (load queue)
53	Guarded load miss (cyc)	Cycles stalled (guarded)
54	Store queue full (cyc)	Cycles stalled (store queue)
55	Addr. collision (cyc)	Cycles stalled (collision)
56	DTLB miss (cyc)	Cycles stalled (DTLB miss)
57	DTLB busy (cyc)	Cycles stalled (DTLB busy)
58	Misaligned 2nd part (cyc)	Cycles stalled (misaligned)
60	Instr. L1 reloads	I-cache reloads on fetch
61	Instruction fetches	Fetches writing to buffer
62	IMMU TLB-4K reloads	L1 I-MMU 4K reloads
63	IMMU VSP reloads	L1 I-MMU VSP reloads
64	DMMU TLB-4K reloads	L1 D-MMU 4K reloads
65	DMMU VSP reloads	L1 D-MMU VSP reloads
66	L2MMU error misses	I/D TLB error interrupts
67	Branches taken	Completed taken branches
68	BLR taken	Completed BLR instructions
69	Target mispredict (BTB)	BTB target mispredicts
70	Target BLR mispredict (LS)	Link stack mispredicts
71	BTB miss, but taken	BTB miss but taken
72	BTB hit phantom	BTB hit with phantom branch
82	PMC0 overflow	PMC0 wrap-around
83	PMC1 overflow	PMC1 wrap-around
84	PMC2 overflow	PMC2 wrap-around
85	PMC3 overflow	PMC3 wrap-around
86	Interrupts taken	General interrupts taken
87	External input interrupts	External interrupts taken
88	Critical input interrupts	Critical interrupts taken
89	System call/trap interrupts	Syscall & trap interrupts
90	TBL bit transitions	Transitions of TBL bit (PMGC0[TBSEL])
91	PMC4 overflow	PMC4 wrap-around
92	PMC5 overflow	PMC5 wrap-around
97	Stash hit L1 Data Cache	Hits in L1 D-Cache
99	Stash requests L1 Data Cache	Requests to L1 D-Cache
100	LSU thread priority switches	LSU thread priority switches

TABLE X: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 101–150) [2]

Event	Name	Description
101	FPU request denied	Cycles both threads had FPU requests and one was denied
102	VPERM request denied	Cycles both threads had VPERM requests and one was denied
103	VGEN request denied	Cycles both threads had VGEN requests and one was denied
104	CFX request denied	Cycles both threads had CFX requests and one was denied
105	Fetch request denied	Cycles both threads had Fetch requests and one won arbitration
110	LSU issue stalled	Cycles LSU issue queue not empty but 0 instructions issued
111	FPU issue stalled	Cycles FPU issue queue not empty but 0 instructions issued
112	AltiVec issue stalled	Cycles AltiVec issue queue not empty but 0 instructions issued
113	FPU schedule stalled	Cycles FPU not empty but 0 instructions scheduled
114	VPERM schedule stalled	Cycles VPERM not empty but 0 instructions scheduled
115	VGEN schedule stalled	Cycles VGEN not empty but 0 instructions scheduled
116	VPU operand wait	Cycles VPU instruction waits for operands
117	VFPU operand wait	Cycles VFPU instruction waits for operands
118	VSFX operand wait	Cycles VSFX instruction waits for operands
119	VCFX operand wait	Cycles VCFX instruction waits for operands
122	IB empty	Cycles Instruction Buffer is empty
123	IB full	Cycles Instruction Buffer full enough to stop fetch
124	CB empty	Cycles Completion Buffer is empty
125	CB full	Cycles Completion Buffer full enough to stop decode
126	Pre-sync hold	Cycles a pre-sync instruction holds in IB
127	0 instructions completed	Cycles 0 instructions completed
128	1 instruction completed	Cycles 1 instruction completed
129	2 instructions completed	Cycles 2 instructions completed
136	IAC5 detected	Every valid IAC5 detection
137	IAC6 detected	Every valid IAC6 detection
138	IAC7 detected	Every valid IAC7 detection
139	IAC8 detected	Every valid IAC8 detection
140	IAC1 detected	Every valid IAC1 detection
141	IAC2 detected	Every valid IAC2 detection
142	IAC3 detected	Every valid IAC3 detection
143	IAC4 detected	Every valid IAC4 detection
144	DAC1 detected	Every valid DAC1 detection
145	DAC2 detected	Every valid DAC2 detection
148	DVT0 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT0 set
149	DVT1 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT1 set
150	DVT2 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT2 set

TABLE XI: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 151–196) [2]

Event	Name	Description
151	DVT3 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT3 set
152	DVT4 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT4 set
153	DVT5 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT5 set
154	DVT6 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT6 set
155	DVT7 detected	Write to DEVENT SPR with DVT7 set
156	Cycles stalled (Nexus)	Completion cycles stalled due to Nexus FIFO full
161	FPU finish	FPU finish
162	FPU divide cycles	Cycles of divide execution
163	FPU denorm input	Extra cycles delay due to denorm inputs
164	FPU denorm output	FPU denorm output
165	FPU FPSCR stall	FPSCR full stall
166	FPU pipe sync stall	Stalls due to FPU sync (break-before/after)
167	FPU input data stall	Stall due to unavailable operands
168	FPU flags	FPU sets FPSCR[FEX]
172	PW20 count	Entries into PW20 power state
176	Decorated loads	Loads to cache-inhibited memory
177	Decorated stores	Stores to cache-inhibited memory
179	stbcx./sthcx./stwcx./stdcx. succ.	Successful conditional stores
180	stbcx./sthcx./stwcx./stdcx. unsucc.	Unsuccessful conditional stores
181	LSU micro-ops	Completed LSU micro-ops
182	GPR loads	Completed GPR loads
183	GPR stores	Completed GPR stores
184	Cache ops	Completed cache ops
185	Memory barriers	Completed memory barriers
186	SFX micro-ops	Completed SFX micro-ops
187	SFX single-cycle	Completed single-cycle SFX ops
188	SFX double-cycle	Completed double-cycle SFX ops
190	CFX instructions	Completed CFX instructions
191	SFX or CFX instructions	Completed SFX or CFX instructions
192	FPU instructions	Completed FPU instructions
193	FPR loads	Completed FPR loads
194	FPR stores	Completed FPR stores
195	FPR loads+stores	Completed FPR loads and stores
196	FPR single-precision	Completed single-precision loads/stores

TABLE XII: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 197–235) [2]

Event	Name	Description
197	FPR double-precision loads and stores completed	FPR double-precision load and store micro-ops completed
198	AltiVec instr. completed	AltiVec instructions completed (non-LSU)
199	AltiVec VSFX instr.	AltiVec VSFX instructions completed
200	AltiVec VCFX instr.	AltiVec VCFX instructions completed
201	AltiVec VPU instr.	AltiVec VPU instructions completed
202	AltiVec VFPU instr.	AltiVec VFPU instructions completed
203	VR loads completed	Vector register load micro-ops completed
204	VR stores completed	Vector register store micro-ops completed
205	VSCR[SAT] set	Number of times saturate bit flips 0→1
210	Cycles SFX0 idle	Cycles Simple Fixed Point Unit 0 idle
211	Cycles SFX1 idle	Cycles Simple Fixed Point Unit 1 idle
212	Cycles CFX idle	Cycles Complex Fixed Point Unit idle
213	Cycles LSU idle	Cycles Load Store Unit idle
214	Cycles BU idle	Cycles Branch Unit idle
215	Cycles FPU idle	Cycles Floating Point Unit idle
216	Cycles VPU idle	Cycles AltiVec Permute Unit idle
217	Cycles VFPU idle	Cycles AltiVec Floating Point Unit idle
218	Cycles VSFX idle	Cycles AltiVec Simple Fixed Point Unit idle
219	Cycles VCFX idle	Cycles AltiVec Complex Fixed Point Unit idle
221	D-L1 misses	Data L1 cache misses (load, store, cache ops)
222	D-L1 load misses	Data L1 cache load misses
223	D-L1 store misses	Data L1 cache store misses
224	LMQ allocates	Loads allocating into Load Miss Queue
225	Load thread miss collision	Load hits line valid for other thread only
226	Status array collision	Collisions on status array access
227	SGB allocates	Store Gather Buffer allocates
228	SGB gathers	Store Gather Buffer gathers
229	SGB overflows	Store Gather Buffer overflows
230	SGB promotions	Store Gather Buffer promotions
231	SGB in-order promotions	In-order promotions or oldest-entry timeout
232	SGB out-of-order promotions	Out-of-order promotions
233	SGB high-priority promotions	Promotions due to load hits on pending store
234	SGB miso promotions	Store Gather Buffer miso promotions
235	SGB watermark promotions	Store Gather Buffer watermark promotions

TABLE XIII: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 236–265) [2]

Event	Name	Description
236	SGB overflow promotions	Store Gather Buffer overflow promotions
237	DLAQ full cycles	Cycles the DLink Age Queue is full
238	DLAQ full times	Times the DLink Age Queue is full
239	LRSAQ full cycles	Cycles the Load Reservation Set Age Queue is full
240	LRSAQ full times	Times the Load Reservation Set Age Queue is full
241	FWDAQ full cycles	Cycles the Forward Age Queue is full
242	FWDAQ full times	Times the Forward Age Queue is full
243	STQ collision forwardable (times)	Store Queue collisions forwardable (not forwardable if store doesn't contain load, cache-inhibited, denormalized FP, store conditional, or guarded load)
244	STQ collision forwardable (times data ready)	Forwardable collisions with data ready
245	STQ collision forwardable (times data not ready)	Forwardable collisions without data ready
246	STQ collision not-forwardable	Collisions not forwardable, must wait until store leaves queue
247	STQ collision forwardable (cycles)	Cycles a forwardable collision lasts
248	STQ collision forwardable (cycles data ready)	Cycles forwardable collision with data ready lasts
249	STQ collision forwardable (cycles data not ready)	Cycles forwardable collision without data ready lasts
250	STQ collision non-forwardable (cycles)	Cycles non-forwardable collision lasts
251	False EA collisions	Times false load-on-store replay due to 12-bit EA match only
252	LS0 result bus collisions	LS0 result bus collisions (around 3 cycles penalty)
253	Inter-thread DW bank collisions	Inter-thread doubleword bank collisions (around 3 cycles penalty)
254	Instruction L1 misses	Instruction L1 demand fetch misses (excludes prefetch)
256	IMMU misses	Misses in level 1 Instruction MMU
257	IMMU TLB4K hits	Hits in level 1 Instruction MMU TLB4K
258	IMMU VSP hits	Hits in level 1 Instruction MMU VSP
259	IMMU tablewalk cycles	Cycles spent in hardware tablewalk
260	DMMU misses	Misses in level 1 Data MMU
261	DMMU TLB-4K hits	Hits in level 1 Data MMU TLB-4K
262	DMMU VSP hits	Hits in level 1 Data MMU VSP
263	DMMU tablewalk cycles	Cycles spent in DMMU hardware tablewalk
264	L2MMU misses	Misses in level 2 MMU
265	L2MMU-4K hits	Hits in L2MMU-4K

TABLE XIV: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 266–471) [2]

Event	Name	Description
266	L2MMU-VSP hits	Hits in level 2 MMU VSP
267	L2MMU indirect misses	Indirect entry lookups without a match
268	L2MMU indirect valid misses	Indirect entry valid but PTE invalid or insufficient
269	LRAT misses	Logical to Real Address Translation misses
272	LMQ loses to SGB	Cycles LMQ loses DLINK arbitration to SGB
273	SGB loses to LMQ	Cycles SGB loses DLINK arbitration to LMQ
274	Thread loses to other	Cycles thread loses DLINK arbitration to the other thread
278	Decode mask/value event	Instructions counted in Decode via mask/value
443	DLINK request	DLINK requests from core to Shared L2
444	ILINK request	ILINK requests from core to Shared L2 (fetches + table-walks)
445	RLINK request	RLINK requests from Shared L2 to core (reload data)
446	BLINK request	BLINK requests from Shared L2 to core (invalidates, stashes, barriers)
447	CLINK request	CLINK requests from Shared L2 to core (CoreNet data forwarding)
456	L2 hits	L2 Cache hits (0–4 per cycle)
457	L2 misses	L2 Cache misses (0–4 per cycle)
458	L2 demand accesses	L2 Cache demand accesses (0–4 per cycle)
459	L2 accesses	All L2 Cache accesses (0–4 per cycle)
460	L2 store allocates	L2 Cache store allocates (0–4 per cycle)
461	L2 instruction accesses	L2 Cache instruction accesses (0–4 per cycle)
462	L2 data accesses	L2 Cache data accesses (0–4 per cycle)
463	L2 instruction misses	L2 Cache instruction misses (0–4 per cycle)
464	L2 data misses	L2 Cache data misses (0–4 per cycle)
465	L2 hits per thread	L2 Cache hits per thread (0–4 per cycle)
466	L2 misses per thread	L2 Cache misses per thread (0–4 per cycle)
467	L2 demand accesses per thread	L2 Cache demand accesses per thread (0–4 per cycle)
468	L2 store allocates per thread	L2 store allocates per thread (0–4 per cycle)
469	L2 instruction accesses per thread	Instruction accesses per thread to L2 (0–4 per cycle)
470	L2 data accesses per thread	Data accesses per thread to L2 (0–4 per cycle)
471	L2 instruction misses per thread	Instruction misses per thread in L2 (0–4 per cycle)

TABLE XV: List of EMs in the T2080 (IDs 472–511) [2]

Event	Name	Description
472	L2 data misses per thread	Data operation misses in L2 per thread
473	L2 reloads from CoreNet	L2 reloads from CoreNet
474	L2 stash requests	Incoming L2 stash requests
475	L2 stash downgraded to snoops	L2 stash requests downgraded to snoops
476	L2 snoop hits	L2 snoop hits
477	L2 snoops causing MINT	L2 snoops causing MINT
478	L2 snoops causing SINT	L2 snoops causing SINT
479	L2 snoop pushes	L2 snoop pushes
480	Stall for BIB cycles	Stall for Back Invalidate Buffer
482	Stall for RLT cycles	Stall for Reload Table
484	Stall for RLFQ cycles	Stall for Reload Fold Queue
486	Stall for DTQ cycles	Stall for Data Transaction Queue
488	Stall for COB cycles	Stall for Castout Buffer
490	Stall for WDB cycles	Stall for Write Data Buffer
492	Stall for RLDB cycles	Stall for Reload Data Buffer
494	Stall for SNPQ cycles	Stall for Snoop Queue
506	BIU master requests	Master transaction starts to CoreNet
507	BIU master global requests	Global master transactions to CoreNet
508	BIU master data-side requests	Data-side master transactions to CoreNet
509	BIU master instruction-side requests	Instruction-side master transactions to CoreNet
510	Stash requests	Stash requests matching stash IDs
511	Snoop requests	External snoop requests from CoreNet